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ESIRA – ENHANCING SOCIAL INNOVATION IN RURAL AREAS

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MAP IMPLEMENTATION GUIDELINES

Deliverable D3.1

WP3 – Framework setting for MAPs operating as community-led
innovation spaces

Project details

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List of acronyms

Acronyms	Full name
CES	Commonly excluded stakeholders
FAO	Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations
MAA	Multi-actor approach
MAP	Multi-actor platform
QH	Quadruple Helix

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1. Executive summary

Enhancing Social Innovation in Rural Areas (ESIRA) project aims at supporting the development of social initiatives and developing best practices in this area. The results of the project will be determined by the activities of the 9 MAPs to be created within ESIRA.

The multi-actor platforms (MAPs) are society-science-policy interfaces established and active in collaboration aimed at co-defining issues and co-creating solutions for a given topic. They are built on the base of quadruple helix. This helix includes representatives of academia, society, science, and policy. The inclusion of different groups of actors ensures diversity of perspectives and experiences which can help achieve more elaborate and out-of-the-box results.

MAP members must be carefully chosen to achieve the optimal activity of the MAPs. They MAP members must be chosen from the key stakeholder groups identified in the MAP area in relation to social innovations. The invited actors must represent not only all the axes of the quadruple helix but also all the vulnerable groups in the MAP area. The persons to become the MAP members must have the power and legitimacy of their stakeholder group as well as the sense of need and urgency to act and enhance social innovations in the rural areas of their MAP area.

The choice of MAP managers – facilitator and monitor/co-facilitator – is also important for the success of MAP activities. They must have high skills of facilitating, creating inclusive dialogue and innovation spaces for co-creation as well as building capacity for all the MAP members and the skills to observe the interactions among the members.

Deliverable 3.1 “MAP implementation guidelines” serves as a guide for foundation of the ESIRA MAPs and their management at further stages within the project. The following deliverables will offer more insight into best practices for the sustainability of community-led innovation spaces (deliverable 3.2 due in M36) and MAPs sustainability plans (deliverable 3.3 due in M46).

The deliverable can also serve everybody interested in implementing multi-actor approach. Yet, it must be borne in mind that ESIRA's "scalable product" is not a specific social innovation. Its scalable product is its tested, documented, and replicable methodology for building the "stakeholders' networks" and "collaborative capacity" that allow other communities to innovate for themselves.

2. Introduction

Rural areas are facing numerous developmental challenges. Some of the rural stakeholders are members of different vulnerable groups. One of the ways to improve rural resilience and empower the most vulnerable groups is to create social economy initiatives.

Within the ESIRA project 9 multi-actor platforms (MAPs) were created to serve as community-led spaces nurturing social innovations and reinforcing the systemic levers for social economy initiatives, building on previous best practices, and advancing on effective mechanisms for self-governance and effective support.

The deliverable D3.1 MAP implementation guidelines is a reference document for the MAP managers – facilitators and monitors. It demonstrates the multi-actor approach to be applied in ESIRA and presents a set of best practices for setting up MAPs and stimulating the engagement of MAP members.

In the deliverable, there is also a description of the ESIRA MAPs' areas to offer the readers not familiar with the project more insights into their specificity.

The deliverable consists of two main parts. First it presents the concept of the multi-actor platforms. This section is based on a literature review. The second part is devoted to the presentation of the MAPs in the ESIRA project. It is based mainly on the survey conducted among the persons responsible for facilitating and monitoring the MAPs.

3. Multi-Actor platforms – Literature review

The Multi-Actor Approach (MAA) is a method that applies collaboration and participation of different stakeholder groups in a specific process. It stands at the forefront of the collaborative innovation processes, offering a framework for co-creating knowledge and developing robust, context-specific solutions by bringing together diverse stakeholders in a structured and meaningful process. Academic and policy interest in the MAA and its related concepts has grown exponentially, particularly after 2010, driven heavily by the launch of EU policy initiatives like EIP-AGRI (2012) and Horizon 2020 (2014). This trend is visible in bibliometric studies across related participatory fields. For example, a 2024 review of citizen science for soil monitoring found a compound annual growth rate of 11.2% in publications from 2000 to 2024, and a similar steep upward curve is seen in research on Living Labs and co-creative design (European Commission, 2024).

A 2024 bibliometric analysis of agricultural innovation literature (European Commission, 2024) provides further detail on the thematic focus of this expanding field. It identified seven distinct clusters of research themes, including:

1. Agricultural enterprise and innovation policy
2. Market competitiveness
3. Quality of food processing technology
4. Technology innovation for rural development
5. Sustainable development
6. Technology transfer
7. Big data in agriculture
8. Agribusiness and innovation technology

The application and study of the MAA and related platform models show a dual concentration, reflecting the different priorities of funding and development bodies. There is a heavy concentration of policy-driven MAA research in Europe, particularly Western Europe. An analysis of 17 multi-actor partnerships identified five countries with the highest capacity to attract resources and lead such projects: Germany, France, the United Kingdom, Spain, and Belgium (Guerrero-Ocampo et al., 2022). This is attributed to strong research infrastructures and decentralised Rural Development Programmes (which fund OGs) that favour bottom-up, place-based initiatives.

However, a parallel body of literature on Multi-Stakeholder Platforms (MSPs) reveals a second, development-driven concentration. A 2018 systematic literature review on MSPs in emerging economies found that 70% of relevant publications focused on Africa, with

minor shares in Latin America and Asia (Barzola et al., 2020). This reflects the long-standing use of these platforms by development agencies like the FAO and in research-for-development projects.

To maximize the effectiveness of MAPs during the project, and impacts after the project ends, selection of MAP members in ESIRA was done using Quadruple Helix (QH) (Schutz et al., 2019) innovation approach as a methodology to involve actors from 4 groups (helixes): civil society, policy, business and academia (Fig. 1). This approach helps solve complex problems as within the MAPs diverse expertise and experiences are represented. The MAP members interact and collaborate with one another.

Figure 1: The quadruple helix model

Source: Schütz et al. (2019), Fig. 1.

The studies show that co-producing knowledge via dialogue in rural areas can:

- Ensure inclusive knowledge production and sharing among different actors (Mwantimwa and Ndege, 2024);
- Help in dealing with a lack of trust between local actors and central governments, which is important especially in rural areas (Beer, 2014; Lewis, 2018);
- Create common visions for sustainable regional development with a commitment to implementation (Bourgoin et al. 2011, McCall and Dunn, 2012);
- Strengthen the resilience and economic competitiveness of rural areas, if the multi-actor group is open to combining different types of knowledge and experiences (Medema et al. 2014; Wellbrock et al. 2013).

The literature review shows that multi-actor platforms are used as a tool for social innovation, sustainable transition and co-governance (Esposito, 2025; Campomoria and Casula, 2023). It is worth mentioning that the literature review shows diversity of definitions and terminology. It seems that in recent years, more studies used the term “living labs”.

The multi-actor approach is a vital part of the EU research philosophy. "(...) the implementation of the multi-actor approach introduced under Horizon 2020 is key for generating impact and co-ownership of solutions. Knowledge exchange will speed up innovation and bring knowledge to the places where it is most useful and needed" (European Commission, 2016).

Although highly appreciated and applicable in different setting, multi-actor approach (MAA) has also certain limitations. The main relate to the following challenges:

- **High Transaction Costs:** Meaningful collaboration is resource-intensive, requiring significant time and budget for coordination, meetings, and facilitation, which can be a barrier for less-resourced actors.
- **Risks of Tokenism and Co-Option:** A constant risk exists that participation becomes a "box-ticking exercise" ("tokenism") to legitimise pre-determined agendas, or that the process is captured by the most powerful actors ("co-option").
- **Difficulty of Measuring Social Impact:** The most valuable outcomes of the MAA are often intangible social and relational changes—increased trust, new networks, enhanced collaborative capacity. These are "difficult to measure" with standard project metrics (e.g., KPIs, deliverables) and may only become visible long after a project ends.
- **Challenge of Scaling Innovations:** An innovation co-developed in a specific local context is not automatically transferable. "Scaling-out" (replication) is challenging because the innovation's success is "deeply tied to the local social context" and the trust-building process that created it.

The stakeholder salience model will be used as a methodology to identify suitable MAP actors in terms of power, urgency, and legitimacy to act in the field of intervention. Business Model Canvas methodology will be used to design new social economy initiatives and revitalize existing MAP members should be stakeholders those who possess some combination of:

- power,
- legitimacy,
- urgency (time sensitivity and criticality).

Theory of stakeholder salience (which entails a cumulating assessment of stakeholders' power, urgency, and legitimacy) helps managers employ skill and judgement in the task of prioritizing stakeholders. The model ensures "purposive processes of organization aimed at being aware of, identifying, understanding, prioritizing, and engaging stakeholders" (Mitchel et al, 2017). The salience model helps at all the stages of functioning of the MAPs to effectively and efficiently organize the process of achieving

the expected goals of the co-creation via the cooperation among the representatives of all groups included in the quadruple helix.

Stakeholder awareness

At this stage MAP managers must assess the potential input to the MAP's objectives of the stakeholder in question. First the surrounding of the planned MAP has to be strategically analysed. Further, **the potential role and engagement of the different stakeholder groups must be assessed**. It is necessary to identify not only these groups and their key representatives but also the linkages and interlinks among these groups to understand the potential conflicts or willingness to cooperate in co-creation.

Stakeholder identification

It is the next step in the stakeholder salience. It is necessary to identify not only these groups and their key representatives but also the **linkages and interlinks among these groups** to understand the potential conflicts or willingness to cooperate in co-creation. The key issue is to invite to the MAP these actors who are the best representatives of the key stakeholder groups – both with power and legitimacy to represent their group as well as have the willingness and urgency.

Stakeholder understanding

At the stage of inviting key stakeholders to become actively involved in the MAP operations it is crucial to get an understanding of the stakeholders' needs and expectations related to their MAP membership. The invited people must receive detailed explanations of **what they can expect and what they can gain from participation in the MAP**. The risk of disappointment must be minimized to avoid resigning from the MAP activities during the MAP operations as it can disturb the whole process.

Stakeholder prioritization

This element of stakeholder salience calls for rethinking the MAP composition with the MAP's *raison d'être* in mind. **The number of MAP members is limited** due to the interoperability of the MAP activities. Each stakeholder's priorities must not only be identified but also understood and compared with the other invited stakeholders.

Stakeholder engagement

It is a constant task for the MAP managers ever since receiving their acceptance to become a MAP member. This task involves careful monitoring of the level of engagement of each of the stakeholders and their interactions with one another.

The engagement of individual MAP members is conditioned by numerous factors including personal characteristics of the members and the environment for the cooperation within the MAP. MAP managers must create capacity building and inclusive environment. To achieve this a skilled facilitator should be chosen for this position.

It is useful to follow the example of the SHERPA project (<https://rural-interfaces.eu/>) in which four guiding principles were applied to setting-up MAPs:

First guiding principle: flexible programming

Adopt an approach of flexible programming to allow timely contributions to policy-making at the EU level. This flexibility concerns both content and timing. It will be achieved with Dynamic Action Plans (DAPs). The aim of this approach is to guarantee timely contributions for the preparation of future policy, and to adapt functioning platforms to new needs and challenges as they arise.

Second guiding principle: co-construction

This means co-constructing (co-producing) recommendations for future policy and research requirements, new initiatives, products or services. Making practical recommendations that can be implemented requires a strongly participatory approach, which can be used as a tool in new public governance (Sorrentino et al., 2018). In this approach information is gathered on the needs and experience of the final beneficiaries of policy, and which involves other stakeholders. Within each MAPs, activity should be focused in a way that maintains discussion and dialogue with representatives of society (e.g. civic society bodies, citizens), alongside decision-makers in charge of designing future policies, and researchers. Members of the MAP should be able to express themselves freely and should be treated equally.

Third guiding principle: multi-level interactions

This is about ensuring fruitful interaction among actors at multiple levels of governance (from local to the EU). Consideration needs to be given to multiple levels of interaction within local, regional and national policy-making, to the European 'landscape', and to the global context. The outcomes of debates within the MAP will support the development of policies at the EU level. So, each MAP will provide inputs (through MAP Position Papers) which will be discussed at EU level. Results will then be debated at the EU-level MAP and discussed as part of the next SHERPA annual conference. Output from MAPs, as presented in their Position Papers, will serve to formulate recommendations for future EU research agendas and rural policies.

Fourth guiding principle: impartiality and transparency

Impartiality and transparency will be ensured through three main mechanisms:

1. Multiple contributions and peer review: each public document produced by a MAP should be prepared by multiple contributors. Each document should be peer-reviewed.

2. Documentation: the outcomes of consultations and discussions organised within each MAP should be documented and should be available for scrutiny by members of the MAPs.

3. Publication: A summary of the Dynamic Action Plans and Position Papers prepared by MAPs will be made publicly available (i.e. they will be published on the project website)” (SHERPA, 2020).

See Figure 2 to know other examples of the multi-actor approach in Horizon Europe projects.

Figure 2 Examples of the multi-actor approach in Horizon Europe projects

	<p>Community-Led Creation of Living Spaces in Shifting Landscapes for Climate-Resilient Land Use Management and Supporting the New European Bauhaus</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Each Living Space represents a different regional context, capturing Europe’s rich diversity of landscapes, climates, ecosystems, and socio-economic realities. • LandShift believes that sustainable change must be co-created, tested, and validated in real-world conditions, with the full involvement of the people who live and work with the land every day. <p><u>Our Living Spaces enable us to:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Co-create solutions with local communities, land managers, researchers, and policymakers. • Adapt innovation to local realities, ensuring that strategies are regionally relevant and acceptable. • Demonstrate scalable models that can inspire wider adoption across Europe. • Test and validate new approaches using advanced monitoring, Earth Observation, and data-driven decision-support systems. • Each LS is more than just a site. It is a hub of collaboration, experimentation, and empowerment. 	
	<p>Spreading Open and Inclusive Literacy and Soil Culture through Artistic Practices and Education</p>
<p>Each Soil Orchestra brings together a small, diverse group of 15 to 30 individuals from across the arts, sciences, education, policy, and community sectors. Together, they will:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Design and carry out creative and interdisciplinary projects related to soil knowledge and preservation, including the organisation of soil festivals; – Develop skills on soil and art issues; – Participate in national and European exchanges to consolidate the projects of the Soil Orchestra in each country; – Contribute to the broader objective of anchoring soil culture in the cultural life of the country, in particular by promoting the projects selected in the SOILSCAPE open calls. 	

Source: Own elaboration based on <https://landshift.eu/> and <https://soilscape.eu/>

4. Multi-Actor platforms in ESIRA

In the ESIRA project, Multi-Actor Platforms (MAPs) are community-led, place-based innovation ecosystems enacting the multi-actor approach of the project and its vision for community-led spaces. They will strengthen the applicability and impact of the solutions and other project findings and will provide the knowledge to create a bridge between practitioners and science; co-generate the innovations produced by the project, focusing on the usability of the results, and therefore facilitating replication.

MAP framework needs to be flexible enough to fit the different social and behavioural contexts of each pilot, looking for the maximum representativeness of the local actors (including gender, age, socioeconomic level perspective) and putting in place different mechanisms to encourage the empowerment of the vulnerable groups of the population.

MAP managers must continue the screening of local actors already offered at the proposal stage, so the different case study MAPs can be kicked off as soon as possible in the project, maximum by M6.

Some indicators have been defined to ensure representativeness although they will be flexible depending on each case: share of female participants (40-60%), share of members in the age 65+ (>15%), share of members in the age 30- (>15%), and diversity of stakeholder groups by sector: none of them should have a share > 40%.

This section consists of two parts. In the first one, the applied approach to MAP functioning in ESIRA is presented. In the second part the ESIRA MAP characteristics are presented.

4.1 Multi-actor approach applied in the project

4.1.1 Roles in MAPs

As mentioned earlier in the theoretical framework there are several roles identified in a MAP. The key role is played by the facilitator. In the process, this person is accompanied by a monitor (co-facilitator). MAP is made up of the members described above. For a better understanding of the whole process, we indicate as a separate role the MAP meeting.

a) Facilitator

Nansen Centre for Peace and Dialogue (NCPD), a recognized Norwegian organization which promotes a dialogic approach, describes the facilitation as follows: "The noun facilitator comes from the Latin word "facilitare," meaning "to facilitate a process," with a facilitator being a person who creates space for a group process characterized by openness and respect. A person who performs the function of a facilitator in this way is filled with humility and readiness to provide support, which empowers participants and

prompts them to share their knowledge and experience. The facilitator is impartial and does not interfere in the group's decision-making process, while at the same time he or she must make sure that everyone's input is considered. The facilitator makes sure that each participant feels comfortable and safe to take part in the conversation, solve problems and conflicts, and make decisions independently. This can be achieved through active listening, asking good questions, paraphrasing and summarizing.”

Facilitator in ESIRA project is responsible for the following tasks:

- Invites and enrolls MAP members;
- Creates a feeling of security and trust;
- Supports the MAP in achieving objectives;
- Summarises the outcomes;
- Prepares Position Paper - MAP's position on the topic / policy recommendations;
- Shares knowledge from research with MAP.

Facilitator is more in the field, closer to the group, takes care of the atmosphere at meetings and keeps an eye on the rules of dialogue conversation; is on the driving seat of the MAP. That is why it is so important to select the right person to perform this function.

b) Monitor / co-facilitator

The second important role in MAP is played by the monitor. Sometimes, depending on the MAP, the monitor will act as a co-facilitator. The monitor:

- Assists the facilitator by adding reflexivity, co-facilitation;
- Documents progress;
- Reflects on MAP functioning;
- Reports and evaluates the work.

Monitor hides a bit in the shadows, over-supervises the work of the facilitator and the group. Monitor domain: observe, assess, capture and report on progress on targets.

c) MAP members (described above)

d) MAP meetings

MAP Meetings are conducted in a spirit of dialogue. They are accompanied by equality, a sense of security and a friendly, informal atmosphere. An important part of the meetings, and also a good practice, is to provide snacks and drinks during the meetings. Hungry MAP members will be less engaged in the whole process, so when organizing such meetings, it is worth taking this aspect into account. It is also important to remember that MAP meetings require the consent of the participants, so each member should give such consent in writing before starting. It is a good idea to take photos, document each of the meetings for dissemination purposes with MAP members to participate in the project.

MAP meeting is an opportunity to network MAP members who may never have had the chance to meet if it were not for this project.

Figure 3 MAP BIESZCZADY meeting, Wetlina, Poland 2023

Source: Ewa Żechowska, Chata Wędrowca Nr 13 (<https://chatatrzynastka.pl>)

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4.1.2 Communication

Communication is a complex process. The way we communicate depends on our past experiences, values, current attitudes, thoughts, context and feelings. The Iceberg Model explains it well.

Figure 4 Iceberg Model

Source: <https://therightquestions.co/the-iceberg-model-of-organisational-culture/>

The MAP approach allows us to gather comprehensive, valuable, in-depth information because we can go from the declarative level and see what's happening at other levels. We start by listening...

“Whether we can communicate well depends on our ability to reflect on how we communicate. Our body expresses much more than words. Clarity about how to interpret body language affects our understanding of verbal messages. That's why, to avoid misunderstandings, it's so important to listen properly and ask questions that can keep us from misunderstanding. the message” (NCPD, 2018).

You have a great opportunity to discover more and more complex things during MAP meetings, especially offline.

Figure 5 Three levels of listening

Source: NCPD (2018), *The Nansen Handbook for Trainers in Dialogue and Conflict Transformation*, p.15.

Dialogue

The approach that works in organizing MAP's life is dialogue. Dialogue is not a debate, is not a discussion. Dialogue is about listening to each other, not convincing each other to be right.

"Dialogue is a way of communicating, in which we focus on understanding the "other" instead of convincing him or her of our rightness. Such understanding enables us to build lasting relationships and lay a strong foundation" (NCPD, 2018, p.8).

"Dialogue is a process of real, mutual interaction, in which people listen to each other enough attentively that they can change under the influence of what they learn. Each participant in a dialogue tries to consider the other person's point of view even when contradictions persist. None of the participants dialogue does not abandon his or her own identity, but each recognizes the position of the other person that he or she changes his or her conduct towards it." (Pruitt and Philip, 2007).

Figure 6 Nansen Center for Peace and Dialogue publications

Source: <https://nansen.peace.no/download-category/publikasjoner/>

4.1.3 Life of the MAP – three stages

There are three stages in the life of every MAP: establishing, sustaining and “life after life”.

a) First Stage: Establish the MAP (manager/facilitator/monitor + members)

Two things are key in this stage:

1. Find the MAP manager/facilitator who knows and feels the MAP area. As mentioned earlier, the Facilitator should speak the same language, has good communication and leadership skills and enjoys working with people and not taking the whole space.
2. Find members who meet the criteria and get in touch with them. Important is to establish relationships, not just contacts. This is also the moment to find the best way to communicate – every MAP is different, so approach in every MAP will be different.

In this stage there are essential questions to answer:

- Where to find right people?
- How many people?
- The best channel of communication?
- Online, offline, mix?
- Formal, informal?

Before working with MAP members, each of these questions should be reflected upon and a decision should be made on what the background of our MAP should look like.

Good practices

Experience from the SHERPA project, among others, has yielded good practices. It is worth taking a look at them and seeing which ones are worth implementing in a MAP:

- Use as simple language as you can. Do not use specialised, scientific language. There will be people from different backgrounds in MAP. Ensure that the language you use is understandable and inclusive by all.
- Don't send too many messages, don't hold more meetings for MAP members than necessary. We all have limited time - let's use it as efficiently as possible. If we want to keep the group engaged, ensure that the group does not feel overwhelmed by us.
- Local leaders have a lot of friends and can encourage them to take part in the project. The important thing is to convince the leaders that the ESIRA project is valuable, and their participation is meaningful. If you find that the MAP composition is not entirely effective, it is through the leaders that you can more easily recruit more people.
- Don't just focus on meetings, only on verbal and written communication with MAP members. Get a feel for the area being explored. Participatory observation comes to the rescue. To get a good understanding of the processes that are going on, the motivations of people, you need to go beyond the declarative level.
- We can get many members to join our MAP, but we need to know how to reach them:

"I would be happy to talk to you, but I must tell you straight away - I will not be filling in any questionnaire. I don't have time for that. But you are welcome to join me for coffee."
(Deputy mayor, SHERPA MAP Bieszczady, Poland)

REMEMBER: We work with social inclusion, so everything we do with MAP should be inclusive.

b) Second stage: Sustaining the MAP activities, keeping members engaged

Find your own way to keep participants engaged - you know best what motivates them to participate, what is important to them.

We will share our experiences. For example, for our MAP members the most important was:

- Opportunity to meet other interesting people & networking;
- Opportunity to exchange experiences;
- Meeting in the spirit of dialogue, in a friendly atmosphere, with people from different "information bubbles";
- Willingness to take part in something that matters - possibility to be heard;
- Opportunity to explore a new place in the region.

MAP activities

MAP activities depend on the specifics of your area and the people participating. Don't do anything by force. See what works best for you and go that route. And if you see that the path taken is not working, change direction. Just remember not to push the intensity too far.

The most typical MAP activities are:

- Offline MAP meetings. This is the most important activity. We recommend one or two per year with as many members as possible.
- Online MAP meetings. If it is not possible to meet offline, it is worth using this form.
- Interviews. One-to-one interviews, diads, triads, group interviews. When MAP members can't make it to a MAP meeting, this is a great way to include them the group's activities.
- Email communication. Do not advise emailing MAP members with too many questions or surveys.
- Communication through social media. For some MAP is a good solution, for others it is not. Some prefer closed groups on Facebook or through communicators (Messenger, WhatsApp). You need to adjust the activities so that they are not exclusionary. Not every MAP member can use social media.
- Participatory observation (and non-participatory observation). This activity mainly concerns the facilitator and monitor but may also involve other members.
- Tasks. Well-planned, meaningful tasks can help integrate the group, cement it, and enable it to digest a long time.

c) Third stage: MAP after the project

Once the project is completed, think about how to use the potential of MAP in other projects - it would be a shame to waste the relationships established and the way of working with MAP that has been developed.

Table 1 Risks identified in ESIRA in relation to MAPs and the mitigation measures

Risk	Mitigation measures
Low facilitation skills of MAP facilitators.	The train-the-trainers programme will provide training and mentoring to support facilitators in their activities. Continuing monitoring of MAP activities will provide immediate feedback so additional materials and support can be provided throughout the project.
Low interest and engagement of MAP members. MAPs characteristics show the lack of engagement of some groups in some pilots (youth under 30). The voluntary engagement of stakeholders in MAPs and community-led innovation spaces ensures participants' intrinsic interest, but it also raises questions about the operational stability of these structures.	The analysis of specific needs will be done to identify relevant topics for MAP activities and the invitation of relevant stakeholder groups, trying to increase the attractiveness of being part of the MAP. Pinares Burgos-Soria MAP has designed a specific training programme for young people to attract them to the MAP activities.
Lack of involvement of vulnerable groups. MAPs' characteristics indicate a lack of engagement among some vulnerable groups in some pilots (for example, migrants).	Each partner will establish an agreement with local NGOs and associations to ensure participation of this group. Also, specific communication activities will be carried out. Some MAPs have already established communications with local NGOs to carry out activities with minority groups (Hungarian MAP).
Lack of motivation and social, economic and institutional organisational structure to give continuity to the project in the rural territory once the project has ended.	Establishment of community links between the entities participating in the project, the social, economic and institutional agents of the territory (design of a collaborative network).

Source: ESIRA Proposal and D5.1

4.2 Key characteristics of the ESIRA MAPs

4.2.1 MAPs and their communities

There are 9 MAPs in the ESIRA project. The areas were chosen to ensure a broad variety of the EU settings and diversity of vulnerable groups, that is the so-called commonly excluded stakeholders (Davis et al., 2025).

In this sub-section the key characteristics of ESIRA MAP areas are briefly presented (Table 2). The information about the managing teams was gathered through the survey to identify the characteristics of settings in which they conduct their activities related to ESIRA project.

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Table 2 ESIRA MAPs' areas and their characteristics

ESIRA MAP	Vulnerable groups	Social economy	Existing innovation ecosystem
Burgos, ES	Women, elder, youth, migrants	The wood-related industry is of foremost importance in the region, as municipalities owns 80% of the total area (communal property of the forest), being timber harvesting a traditional activity done by neighbours. Some R&D activities look into the potential of forestry-related activities and there is already public support mechanisms. Cultural and natural tourism activities are also a remarkable booster of the local economy. The following topics are identified as priorities: cultural initiatives, digital literacy and services, new transport models, labour inclusion, natural resources preservation and management, housing access for migrants and neo-rurals.	SODEBUR is the public entity promoting the social and economic development throughout the province's municipalities. FO2 is an active NGO working on the promotion and development of social, cultural and environmental values. Some other external entities have been tagged as potential collaborators during the project, such as the Office of Innovation against Depopulation, the Digital Valley, AGALSA, ASOPIVA, CESEFOR foundation, SIERRA DE LA DEMANDA rural co-working, etc. Different associations, networks or social enterprises working in the county in different issues related to rural development.
Abruzzo, IT	Erdely people, women	Abruzzo, due to a highly mountainous territory, has always been considered as a marginal region. Despite this, in recent years the region has experienced a significant change thanks to a profound push towards social innovation that comes precisely from the internal areas. Examples in this sense come from the flourishing of energy communities (Gagliano Aterno), community cooperatives (Campo di Giove, San Vincenzo Valle Roveto) and digital welfare initiatives (Calascio). The Abruzzo Region itself has begun to address local needs with a special focus on the health and well-being for all and for all ages, an inclusive and	BorghilN – Network of Cooperatives of Abruzzo is a network of companies consisting of about 50 non-profits. The Network develops territorial welfare dynamics by implementing structural partnerships and integrated economic and sustainable actions which foresee the active participation of the inhabitants and of the residents, in order to pursue the collective well-being of communities, valuing local resources, tangible and non-tangible heritage. The Network is inspired by the principles dictated by the goals of the 2030 Agenda on sustainability, the Faro Convention on communities of legacy (Council of

		sustainable economic growth, equal opportunities and digitization.	Europe) and the Confcooperative Habitat charter on the value of inhabiting the places.
Trento, IT	People with disabilities, women and youth NEET	The cooperative movement in Trentino has its roots in the XIX century when, in 1895. The widespread presence of cooperative enterprises throughout the Province makes Trentino a genuine “cooperative district” with few analogies around the world, whose features have been assessed by the OECD.	FTC is a cooperative federation that groups almost all the cooperative enterprises of Trentino region (about 500) and counts 255.000 cooperative members (out of app. 500.000 inhabitants). FTC provides assistance, consulting, supervision, political representation and auditing services to cooperative enterprises organized into 5 main sectors: 1) agriculture, 2) retail, 3) labour & services, 4) social & housing and 5) credit. The social sector groups about 56 social cooperatives and provides support for care and assistance to vulnerable and disadvantaged people such as young people and adults who are going through social, personal and economic difficulties, individuals with psychiatric problems, the elderly, people with disabilities and with a migration background.
Northern Hungary and Northern Great Plain, HU	Youth (NEETS), Roma, women	There is not a common legal framework supporting social economy enterprises in the region, although several legal forms are regulated, and there are some wage subsidies for work integration enterprises. However, the specific support depends much more on the municipalities’ funds and support. The following topics are identified as priorities: artisan workshops, local agriculture.	Local NGOs and church charities already work together under the long-term programme “Catching-up settlements” to implement innovative social and economic measures in the most deprived villages of Hungary.

Zachodniopomorskie, PL	NEETS, Youth, women	The Polish Social Economy Act (2022) considers forms of supporting the development of the social economy. There are specific national supporting mechanisms already contemplated in the "Resilience and Development of Social Economy and Social Entrepreneurship" and the National Program for the Development of Social Economy until 2030. Associations and Social Economy Center bring also specific support to social economy initiatives. The following topics are identified as priorities: transport and digital connectivity, diversification of economic activities, stimulation of (young) entrepreneurship.	Several networks operating in the territory will be targeted for cooperation, such as the NDS Fund, the West Pomeranian Network of Social Economy Support Centers, or the Innovation Network in Agriculture and Rural Areas (public entity representing the country in EIP-AGRI).
Leski-Bieszczadzki, PL	Women, migrants, and the elderly	Apart from national programmes, there are also specific public programmes for the Podkarpackie region. The following topics are identified as priorities: transport and digital connectivity, natural resource management and landscape restoration, women-focused social resilience, and migrant-inclusion.	Cluster Podkarpackie Flavours (agri-food local products cluster), "Podkarpacie Country" Quality life cluster (working on sustainable tourism, health and eco-technologies), the Aviation Valley (sectoral association around the regional aviation industry), the Subcarpathian Innovation Center (mainly focused on scientific skills), the Carpathian Tourism Cluster, and the Solina Energy Cluster.
Jablanica & Pčinja Districts, RS	Women, Youth (NEETS)	There is not a national or local framework for supporting social economy initiatives in the Republic of Serbia or the Western Balkans Region. Although the National Employment Service and municipalities support social enterprises through subsidies via Annual Call, still main support for social initiatives comes from international funds and organizations. There is great potential for social enterprises with the development of the Open Balkan as a new, regional cooperation initiative between Albania, North Macedonia, and Serbia. The following topics are identified as priorities: digital transformation, women-focused social resilience, and youth and women entrepreneurship.	IRI has pinpointed the main cooperators in the peri-urban areas under its case study, working fundamentally on the social and economic development through the promotion of business, start ups and local youth initiatives: Center for the Development of Jablanica & Pčinja Districts, Center for Activism Vranje, and the Business Incubator Center Yumco Doo Vranje.

Druskininkai, LT	Youth (NEETS), elder	<p>Apart from the national State Progress Strategy “Lithuania 2050” and National Programme for boosting social inclusion and combating poverty, Druskininkai municipality address the issues of inclusion of vulnerable groups via Druskininkai Municipality Strategic Development Plan for 2021-2029. The following topics are identified as local priorities: Innovative solutions for the provisions of services, new digital tools, inclusive business model innovation, social resilience for the mitigation of labour seasonality, diversified farming.</p>	<p>Since 2009 the Druskininku Local Action Group was aiming to strengthen the community and the local economy in the territory of Druskininkai region and provide an opportunity for local residents to contribute to the development of Druskininkai region. During various events and meetings, day-to-day activities they encouraged residents to inform about existing problems and together to search for a solutions. Activities dedicated to implementing the LAG strategy have helped identify many creative people in the region. Some other entities around the regional ecosystem are identified as potential cooperators, such as the NGO “Salty winds” (innovation ecosystem for equal opportunities of vulnerable groups – small local craftsmen, farmers, artists, etc.), the network Surus Vejai (+25 entities involving +100 local dwellers working on local services and tourism).</p>
Innlandet, Norway	People with disabilities	<p>In Innlandet county there is no framework built specifically for supporting or developing new social economy initiatives. But both the county and the municipalities do offer support for volunteer organisations in a broad range of sectors and activities. The regional plan for social inclusion, “Regional plan for det inkluderende Innlandet aims to establish collaboration with relevant partners from both public and private sectors, as well as NGOs and the academic sector.</p>	<p>Innlandet County role is to work with municipalities, NGOs, businesses and other actors to develop the county in a socially, economic and environmentally sustainable way. The region has a large set of NGOs representing people with different kinds of disabilities, as well as umbrella organisations bringing these NGOs together for collaboration and increased efficacy. IC has its own council for people with disabilities where many of these NGOs are represented. Additional potential have been identified among NGOs, businesses and academia, engaged within both the healthcare and technology innovation sectors.</p>

Source: Own elaboration based on the project’s grant agreement.

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4.2.2 MAP managing teams

The 9 ESIRA MAPs are led by one (6 MAPs) or more (3 MAPs) ESIRA partners. This is a result of consortium composition where some partners, thanks to their close co-operation in the MAP areas together manage the MAP. A survey of MAP managing teams showed that none of the institutions managing the ESIRA MAPs had no prior experience with the multi-actor approach and the majority of them had experience as a leading, managing or facilitating institution of a thematic or project group combining different stakeholders. The same applies to the people responsible for the MAP management as facilitators and monitors.

4.2.3 Resources available to the MAP managing team within ESIRA

Each ESIRA partner responsible for MAP facilitation and monitoring dispose of different budget for activities related to MAPs which is a result both of different MAP regional characteristics and project proposal preparation process. Naturally, all partners have certain flexibility in adjusting the level of resources devoted to MAP activities given the changing costs and MAP dynamics.

Even when it comes to the costs of MAP meetings not in all cases are these costs covered by ESIRA project. In the survey conducted among MAP managers, in four cases, the respondents stated that the costs of organising MAP meetings are only partially covered by ESIRA. When it comes to the remuneration of the MAP managing teams for their activities related to ESIRA MAP functioning, the vast majority of them receive financial remuneration but in the remaining cases, it is only partial.

An even more mixed picture stems from responses to the question on the availability of a budget for MAP members to determine their activities within ESIRA project. The responses were mixed showing that part of the MAPs has such funding and part not but most of the ones not having a budget for activities determined by MAP members plan to do so. It must be mentioned that this is in line with the project phases. The MAPs have already named potential social economy initiatives to be founded in their area and the financial support for their implementation will be needed in a near future. Yet, as these issues are not directly determined in the grant agreement, therefore the MAP managing teams have some room for their own decisions, but at the same time, there are no clear rules to what extent the MAP initiatives can be supported. Among the ones already offering some support, the following response depicts the extent of funding:

“We only provide training and specialized advice to facilitate the access of MAP initiatives to financial resources, as well as guidance to support the inclusion of environmental and social criteria in these initiatives.”

4.2.4 Suggestions concerning needed resources for MAP activities

The MAP managing teams were also asked about their suggestions concerning the **resources that should be offered to MAPs for their activities**. The responses were diverse and related to the **budget level** and structure of the ESIRA partners managing a given MAP. The responses included, i.e., the following statements:

“ESIRA could provide resources specifically dedicated to covering the operating costs of at least one local initiative. These resources are not included in the budget and therefore it is not possible for ESIRA to cover the operating costs of any of the initiatives mapped.”

“A budget should be set aside for:

- train-the-trainers - a series of training sessions, because we do not know what amounts we are dealing with and what we, as MAP Managers, can do, nor what is expected of us - on what scale, how it will translate into action;*
- organizing MAP meetings (catering);*
- budget for mentors/tutors for specific social economy initiatives – specialists who can oversee the process and ensure that the initiative is implemented.”*

“Financial resources (cascade funding from Horizon or another related EU project could be provided to support specific ESIRA MAP activities).”

“We consider three main support areas which might be provided by the ESIRA project to support the ESIRA MAP activities:

Promoting community engagement and strengthening local associations, as a direct response to the demographic decline and weakening of social networks in rural areas.

Encouraging the development of care economy initiatives and cooperatives providing essential services, given that one of the main challenges in the ESIRA rural area is the lack of daily life and work-life balance services. This sector also represents a high employment potential, particularly for women and young people.

Developing a collective digital platform for the management and marketing of locally produced goods (such as mushrooms, timber, and livestock), to support producers who often operate in isolation and have limited access to markets and consumers.”

“Yes. Certain start-up costs should be covered by project grants.”

As an issue of **remuneration of multi-actor group members** is a more and more often discussed question related to the sustainability of these groups, the ESIRA MAP managing teams were asked about their opinions on the topic given their experiences already gained in ESIRA. The possible responses in the survey included:

“Members should be volunteers and only their travel costs should be reimbursed.

Members should be paid a pre-agreed amount for participation in each meeting.

Only a small gift should be offered for participation at the end of the whole project.

Other, please specify:”.

There were only two options chosen by the respondents. Four respondents chose the option of volunteer MAP membership, while the other five opted for “other”.

“The sustainability of the multi-actor group is not so much linked to the remuneration of members for participating in the group and meetings (which may well be on a voluntary basis but with at least a symbolic reimbursement of expenses) as to the sustainability of the initiatives that are proposed and promoted. If the initiatives are based solely on voluntary work, it is not possible to guarantee their sustainability, continuity and quality. If, on the other hand, the initiatives, while making use of voluntary work, require specific professional figures and a guarantee of the quality of the service/performance provided, it is right and necessary to remunerate the professionals who provide their skills.”

“Certain non-financial incentives should be covered, and costs related to travel and accommodation.”

“Any remuneration of MAP members would be beneficial for MAP members, since all members have multiple jobs to cover their daily expenses, and have very little time to participate in MAP meetings – nevertheless, our understanding is that reimbursement for MAP members is against the basic principles of the project.”

“Perhaps members should be paid not necessarily for each meeting but receive a certain amount during the course of the project. This would help keep them motivated, as they do not always see the long-term benefits immediately. Some short-term compensation, aligned with the level of their contribution, can serve as an additional incentive.”

“(…) the participation is entirely voluntary, and no financial compensation is foreseen. During the implementation of the project, the partner organizations cover the costs of training activities, transportation for study visits (buses), light refreshments, guest speakers, and other related expenses. Once the project comes to an end, it will be necessary to identify new funding sources—such as grants or public subsidies—to ensure the continuity of the activities. However, these funds will be used solely to support organizational and operational costs, as the participation of MAP members is conceived as a voluntary and non-remunerated contribution.”

Given the project’s focus on **vulnerable groups in rural communities**, the respondents were also asked if these groups of stakeholders should be offered **additional encouragement for participation** in the MAP. The vast majority of respondents stated that no additional encouragement should be offered. The remaining two responses related to the experiences of the MAP managing teams with the vulnerable groups in their MAPs:

“I think it would be good to be able to offer something more to people with MAP, but not only to excluded groups. I believe there should be an option for small grants for grassroots initiatives. If a group has an idea, why shouldn't they be able to implement it as part of the project?”

“Yes, some groups need additional encouragement. Our experience suggests that engaging with migrant communities and people with disabilities can be challenging, perhaps due to limited prior efforts to reach these groups and to differing degrees of social inclusion among them. In the future, it will be necessary to develop ways of connecting with local associations that work with these vulnerable groups, and to implement working methodologies that facilitate their participation by overcoming barriers. Now, it is a pending task. Although this, the exploration of the territory has not revealed any collective agents (associations or

more informal movements) specifically linked to migrants and people with functional diversity. Therefore, connecting with this group is one of the main issues to be addressed. Furthermore, a large proportion of the participating associations, as well as the individuals who approached ESIRA, can be considered young people.

“Regarding the age issue, older people are also recognized as a vulnerable group in the territory, but it has not been difficult to reach this population group, as they are the most numerous. By contrast, it has been challenging to include young people in the project, given their relatively low presence in the area. Nevertheless, through the pilot we are implementing actions to engage them in the project, (...), a training and participatory space for collective creation focused on co-developing solutions for the territory, especially with young people, and which is currently in progress.”

5. Summary

MAPs in the ESIRA project are flexible platforms composed of people linked to the pilot rural areas, participating either individually or on behalf of institutions (civil society, policy, business and academic) who are active in collaboration and come together to co-define challenges and co-create solutions with the common goal of achieving inclusive rural development through innovative social economy initiatives (Marcos & Pérez, 2025).

Each MAP operates in different ecosystem of socio-economic, institutional and environmental conditions that shape their activities and internal relations among MAP members and their needs related to creating social economy initiatives. The initiatives proposed within each MAP and their further implementation will show the diversity of these social milieus and serve as good practices for other rural communities to initiate their own socio-economic projects.

Being almost in the middle of the ESIRA project implementation period, the experiences of MAP managing teams with setting up and running the ESIRA MAPs and the activities related to them can be summarized as a set of best practices and recommendations in line with the ones identified by Davis et al. (2025) in their study on co-creating nature-based solutions with commonly excluded stakeholders. These best practices stem from the recognition shared by the MAP managing teams that the vulnerable groups are generally face with a multifaceted exclusion as there are different ways and form of exclusion that are generally place-based thus the knowledge of local socio-political and economic relations – official and unofficial is needed to encourage participation and co-operation. Moreover, these stakeholder groups face a mutually reinforcing set of participation barriers which must be tackled to enable their participation. Therefore, the key identified best practices include:

- Intentional inclusion – in ESIRA it was already planned in the project proposal, but it is also a common practice among ESIRA MAP managing teams seen as a constant process of monitoring the barriers faced by the commonly excluded stakeholder groups.
- Trust building – the MAP managing teams ensure transparency related both to their goals as the project consortium team and facilitate building trust among MAP members by animating a friendly and participatory co-governance and co-creation environment.
- Flexible process design – flexibility in ESIRA is built into the project itself and MAP managing teams are encouraged to adapt activity processes within the MAPs to the specificity of their MAPs and locality they operate in.
- Equity and recognition – all the MAP members are treated equally, and their contributions are recognized and appreciated.

- Shared expectations – MAP managing teams constantly ensure that the MAP activities are well-understood and that MAP members have common understanding about the process and potential outcomes.
- Reflexivity and learning – these are among the key characteristics of the ESIRA approach well-presented in the tasks related to monitoring and evaluation both of the MAA process and the process of designing and implementing social economy initiatives.

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7. Annexe 1. Further materials

<https://nati00ns.eu/events/living-lab-essential-how-set-living-lab>

<https://nati00ns.eu/events/governance-and-business-models-setting-living-lab>

https://social-and-creative.interreg-med.eu/fileadmin/user_upload/Sites/Social_and_Creative/horizontal_project/TALIA-policy-briefing8.pdf

https://social-and-creative.interreg-med.eu/fileadmin/user_upload/Sites/Social_and_Creative/horizontal_project/TALIA-policy-briefing7.pdf

https://social-and-creative.interreg-med.eu/fileadmin/user_upload/Sites/Social_and_Creative/horizontal_project/TALIA-policy-briefing-5.pdf

<https://issuu.com/enoll/docs/366265932-u4iot-livinglabmethodology-handbook>

8. Partners

